

TEACHING LAW STUDENTS BY DIFFERENT INNOVATION PEDAGOGICAL METHODS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: In this article, the teaching of English to Uzbek students and the use of various pedagogical innovative approaches and their practical implementation are widely covered.

Аннотация: В данной статье широко освещены преподавание английского языка узбекским студентим, использование различных педагогических инновационных подходов и их практическая реализация.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada talabalarni ingliz tilida o'qitish hamda turli pedagogik innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanish va ularni amalda tatbiq etish keng yoritib berilgan.

Key words: educational material, highly innovative methods, cooperative learning, gamification, innovative teaching strategies

Ключевые слова: учебный материал, высокие инновационные методы, сотрудничество обучения, gamification, инновационные стратегии обучения

Kalit so'zlar: o'quv material, yuqori innovatsion usullar, hamkorlikda o'rganish, o'yinlashtirish, innovatsion o'qitish strategiyalari

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays global change and technological progress, the role of a teacher and mentor becomes essential when each new generation faces a constantly changing world. In Uzbekistan, where traditions of respect for knowledge and those who transmit it are deeply rooted, teachers and mentors are not just transmitters of information, but also key figures in building the country's future. We have greaters such as Alisher Navoi, Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Rayhon Beruni, and hundreds of other great teachers and mentors left their indelible mark, modern education respects the heritage while enriching it with current approaches. Teachers today are not just repositories of knowledge, but also mentors who form young people's spiritual and moral guidelines, helping them navigate a world that is changing daily. They are the arches of a bridge that leads to a future where education meets innovation and modern teaching methods strengthen traditional values. Teachers and mentors in Uzbekistan not only pass on

knowledge, but also help the younger generation find their way in a complex world, supporting their desire for self-development and their place in society.

The new Uzbekistan is actively integrating into the global educational space. In this process, teachers and mentors become indispensable participants in helping to create an education system that meets international standards while preserving national identity. Thus, the future of education in Uzbekistan cannot be imagined without them, which, being the core of the country's development, inspire, motivate, and guide the younger generation to achieve new heights.

On October 1, Uzbekistan celebrates an important and special holiday – Teachers and Mentors Day. This holiday is a tribute of respect and gratitude to those who devoted their lives to science, education, and the upbringing of the younger generation.

In 2023, this holiday takes on special significance, since it falls on the year declared in the country as the Year of Human Care and Quality Education. In addition, the world celebrates the 75th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which affirms the right of every person to education. Following this principle, Uzbekistan sees its teachers and mentors as the central intermediaries in delivering this fundamental right to every citizen.

Teaching young generations through cooperative learning techniques

Nowadays we often hear teachers saying that young generation is a crowd of slackers, arrogant, disloyal, having short attention spans and absolutely uninterested in science. Actually these descriptions are less likely to reflect the behaviors of individuals in young generation than the perceptions of the training process managers who are not attuned to new ways of learning. These characteristics of the young learners reflect the need for the new teaching approaches and modern learning strategies promoted by cognitive scientists, such as learning in context. Learning english and real-world application of knowledge that is a real challenge of the educational process. Paulo Coelho states “People never learn anything by being told, they have to find out for themselves”.

Having grown up with one or both parents working abroad further their education, actual generation learners are used to get things done on their own. Hence, they tend to be independent problem solvers and self-starters. They want support and feedback, but they don't want to be controlled. Because many of them grew up with computers, young generation is technologically literate. They are familiar with computer technology and prefer the

quick access of Internet, CD-ROMs and the World Wide Web as their sources for finding and locating information.

Conditioned to expect immediate gratification present students are responsive. They crave stimulation and expect immediate answers and feedback.

Actual learners are focused on education quality, as they don't want to waste time doing quantities of school work or useless tasks. They want their work to be meaningful to them. "They want to know why they must learn something before they take time to learn it"¹.

Knowing that they must keep learning to be marketable, young learners generation are lifelong learners. They do not expect to grow old working for the same company, so they view their job environments as places to grow. They seek continuing education and training opportunities, if they don't get them, they seek new jobs where they can. Craving success on their own terms, they are ambitious and fearless. Most of them believe "I have to take what I can get in this world because no one is going to give me anything"². Education reflects the effects of a changing society. The learning strategies are usually tied to the learners' needs and interests. Life experiences shape the way people learn.

Teachers must be alert to the need for continual updating of their teaching skills and practices in order to avoid sayings like Wagschal's one who reports: "I'm not sure when it happened. I was no longer a contemporary of my students". Ogden și Richard underline learner's active role in the educational process and affirm that "learning is not a static process, it's an active one in which the learning subjects gives their own meanings to certain things". Effective instruction requires the teacher to step outside the realm of personal experiences into the world of the learner. It is the learner who must be engaged for learning to occur, the learner who must make the commitment to learn. Newmann points out that "learning takes place when students process, interpret and negotiate the meaning of new information. This is heavily influenced by the students' prior knowledge and by the values, expectations, rewards and sanctions that shape the learning environment".

Authentic learning requires the learner to communicate an in-depth understanding of a problem or issue rather than memorize sets of isolated facts and it must result in achievements that have relevance beyond school. Teachers should help students put information to work, to do something, not only know something. They also should engage students in creating their

¹ Caudron S. Can Generation Xers be Trained?, Training and Development 51, no. 3, March, 1997, p. 22.

² Hornblower M. Great Xpectations, Time 129, no. 23, June 9, 1997, p. 62

own learning environments, give them a role in establishing learning goals, high intellectual standards and evaluation criteria, engage learners in projects that demand new skills and the application of existing skills to new situations, challenge them to construct knowledge from their experiences by connecting school learning to life. All these things can be achieved by applying various methods and techniques of cooperative learning. Using cooperative learning, students are continuously discussing, debating and clarifying their understanding of the concepts and materials being considered during the class. They are constructing their own knowledge base. The emphasis is on understanding the material as evidenced by the student's ability to explain ideas to their peers.

This leads to a sense of content mastery versus a passive acceptance of information from an outside expert. This further promotes a sense of helplessness and reliance upon others to attain concepts. Learners who were in classrooms with a significant amount of cooperative learning were psychologically healthier than learners who were not. They had higher self-esteem. Learners in cooperative learning classes have more positive feelings about themselves than do learners in traditional classes. Slavin also documented the findings that these learners had feelings of individual control over their own fate in school, their time on task was higher and their cooperativeness and altruism were higher as well³.

Learners bring with them their own negative attitudes and prejudices. Population diversity is becoming more the norm than the exception in many places. When there is a mix of learners in the same class there is the potential to diminish negative attitudes and to develop positive ones depending how interaction is structured. Cooperative learning structures can be used to develop constructive and supportive peer relationships. Learning environment for the 21st century must be one in which students should be actively engaged in learning activities and with each other. Students nowadays should be all-rounded in order to increase their competitiveness. Cooperative learning offers a proven, practical means of creating exciting social and engaging classroom environment to help students to master traditional skills and knowledge as well as develop the creative and interactive skills needed in today's society and economy. Though cooperative learning had been widely accepted and recommended for language teaching and learning, as discussed in the previous sections, it was by no means a panacea that could solve all the educational

³ Slavin R.E. Cooperative learning: theory, research and practice, Prentice Hall, 1990, p. 123.

problems. There were, like all other teaching methods, limitations in cooperative learning. Most of the limitations of cooperative learning came from not being able to implement the cooperative structure carefully. If the teachers just put the students into groups to learn and didn't structure the positive interdependence and individual accountability, then it would not be unusual to find groups where one person did most (or all) of the work and the others signed off as if they had learned it or had done the work. Or it might be easy to have a "bossy" student who didn't allow the others to take part; or other group dynamic problems that might come from not setting the ground rules for behavior and carefully crafting the group dynamics.

It was also considered time-consuming to teach materials in a cooperative way, although more students might have learned and retained better of the material, as suggested in the Learning Pyramid. This might be true, especially in the beginning when cooperative learning was new to the teacher and to the students. Another concern, according to Turco and Elliott (1990), was that the educational rationale for cooperative learning techniques tended to have been developed more from socialization needs than from achievement needs.

There are many different types of innovative teaching strategies that can be used in teaching. Some examples include

Types of Innovative Teaching Strategies

Project-based learning

Flipped classrooms

Gamification

Inquiry-based learning

Project-based learning: In this strategy, students work together on a project to create a final product. This encourages collaboration and critical thinking skills as they work through complex problems.

Inquiry-based learning: This type of instruction involves asking questions and allowing students to explore the answers through research, experimentation, and discussion.

Flipped classrooms: Flipped classrooms involve using technology such as videos or podcasts to introduce concepts before class time so that during class discussions, teachers can focus more on students

Gamification: Gamification is an approach where instructional materials are designed like games in order to make learning fun and engaging for students.

Implementing Innovative Teaching Strategies

Implementing innovative teaching strategies can be challenging, but with the right resources and support, teachers can successfully incorporate them into their classrooms.

It is important to start by understanding the different **types of innovative teaching** strategies so that you can determine which ones will work best for your students.

Once you have determined which strategies are most appropriate for your classroom, it is essential to provide clear instructions and expectations for the students before beginning a project or activity.

All the materials needed for the activity are available so that students do not get frustrated or overwhelmed when trying to complete their assignments.

And provide guidance and support throughout the process in order to ensure student success. This may take the form of providing feedback on progress made during activities or offering suggestions if a student seems stuck on an idea or problem-solving strategy. It is essential to create an environment where collaboration and experimentation are encouraged – this will help foster creativity among your students as they explore new ideas together!

Final Thoughts on Innovative Teaching Strategies

Innovative teaching strategies are a great way to engage students and foster critical thinking skills in the classroom.

By utilizing different instructional techniques such as project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, flipped classrooms, and gamification – teachers can create an environment where creativity and exploration are encouraged.

These strategies can help improve student engagement and retention, as well as provide teachers with a better understanding of how their students learn best.

Conclusion

Innovative teaching strategies are essential for creating an engaging and effective learning environment for law students. They help teachers to develop creative approaches to instruction, as well as help students become independent learners.

By providing a variety of different instructional strategies and materials, teachers can boost student engagement and achievement in the classroom.

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